

GREEN IT TECHNIQUES FOR ENERGY CONSERVATION

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Abstract:

Green Computing or Green IT is a study that uses science to create technologies that help to preserve natural resources and reduce the harmful impacts on the environment. Green computing, also called green technology, is the environmentally responsible use of computers and related resources to protect environment, minimize energy consumption and to keep the environment Green. The major power consumption components are the central processing unit and the graphic processor unit, chipset etc. So this technology focuses on energy conservation and protecting environment by reducing toxic and hazardous materials. This is done by implementing practices like recycling, electronic waste removal power consumption, implementation of energy efficient peripherals, by reducing resource consumption; by using environmentally friendly products etc. As economy expands the demand for devices increases and they need to be upgraded too due to speed, simplicity, cost effectiveness etc. So it is the time to implement energy efficient CPUs, and other peripherals. Therefore Green IT tries to achieve all these objectives.

Keywords: Energy consumption, Energy efficient, hazardous, Environment, Energy Conservation

1. INTRODUCTION

Green IT is an emerging concept in the field of Computer Science. The main aim of Green IT is to preserve natural resources in an efficient way thereby protecting environment from harmful impacts of toxic and hazardous materials like CFCs. Energy consumption can be made as practical by implementing practices like recycling, use of energy efficient devices, usage of bio-degradable components, etc to keep our nature Green.

Figure 1: Green IT

The need for energy conservation has become a top requirement in all sectors of IT industry. Reduced usage of energy will produce less harm to nature. Keeping our nature Green is to be our motto. To achieve this motto, the Green IT strategy has to be implemented on both large and small scale sectors in IT industry which implies its implementation has to be practised in an organization as well as in an employee's PC.

By applying effective methods of usage of devices, we can save energy even during the device is in idle state. By making Green computing techniques practical, we are also reducing life threatening diseases like cancer, nerve damage and other related problems. The Energy conservation can be done at both hardware and software levels. In software level, energy can be conserved at stages of SDLC (Software Development Life Cycle) like software analysis and during software design by the application of Green techniques. In hardware level, by applying methods like DVFS, enabling sleep mode and by using energy efficient algorithms we can effectively conserve Energy.

2. BENEFITS OF GREEN IT

- Conservation of resources.
- Reduce the risk of harmful and life threatening diseases.
- Recycling waste

- Saving energy by enabling idle condition.
- Power consumption in low cost.
- Sustaining healthy life.
- Conservation of energy of resources at peak times.
- Helps in disposal of electronic waste.
- Reduce causing of damage by reducing emission of CO₂.
- Saving money.
- Usage of Energy efficient devices.
- High accuracy, performance of devices
- Designing things that comply with Environment.
- Telecommunication.
- Environmentally friendly.
- Efficient use of components of the system.

3. CHALLENGES IN IT

- Energy Consumption is very high.
- Greenhouse gas emissions lead to Global warming.
- Generation of e-waste
- Environment pollution caused by processing toxic products.
- Usage of non-biodegradable products.
- High power consumption leads to high electricity bills.
- Risk of life threatening diseases.
- Resource depletion and environmental destruction.
- Climate change
- The gases responsible for Global warming are CO₂, methane etc

Though we have challenges in this field by practising certain techniques of using computing resources, we can efficiently conserve energy.

4. ASPECTS OF ENERGY AND POWER

We can define energy and power in relation with the work system performs. Power is the rate of doing work. Energy is defined as the total amount of work performed over a period of time. It is not possible to measure energy directly; the amount of work done is defined and measured. The generated energy can be stored whereas the power cannot be stored. Power is work/time ratio. It can be calculated using the formula

$$P=W / t \text{ and}$$

$$E=P * t$$

‘w’ denotes work and ‘t’ indicates time.

People use the terms power and energy interchangeably. Energy is the amount of total work done and the power determines how fast we can do a work. By reducing power consumption we can't assure that the effect will reduce the energy consumed.

Our goal is to focus on energy efficient computing. It allows a device to turn to sleep mode after particular time of inactivity. Components like monitors and hard drives can make use of this opportunity. The energy consumption is determined by the amount of energy that is required to operate these devices and how they are utilized. Our ultimate aim is to optimize the amount of energy required to provide products and services which will lead to cost saving. Also it will help to reduce carbon dioxide emissions. This in turn will protect environment from harm and also helps to sustain the balance of nature. Humans will finally benefit from this.

5. ENERGY CONSUMPTION

Consumption of energy in modern computers varies based on the type of work the computer is dealing at that time. We have to consider the energy requirement of each device, when calculating overall energy consumption, because each device or peripheral is contributing a part to the total consumption. The key to reduce this consumption is changing the way how devices are used.

Due to the fast popularity of web based applications, increased number of internet users, we need to store large amount of data to satisfy user's needs. There we need data centers or server farms. Many big companies are investing large into developing new server farms. The concern in this situation is not only power consumption but also energy costs required for heating, ventilating, cooling etc. The energy consumption of computers and monitors vary. It is determined by their energy requirements and usage pattern. Energy efficiency of these peripherals has improved a lot. But at the same time increased processing power in computers and high resolution provided by monitors again increased energy requirements.

We can effectively control energy consumption of these devices. These newer computers and monitors consume more energy when they are in active state, they will consume less energy in low power mode. By knowing the amount of power draw for working, we can know about the energy requirements of computers and monitors. This is determined and measured in watts, which finally indicates the amount of energy a device needs at a particular moment. The main components that consume power are the CPU, hard drives, graphic cards, monitors, scanners, printers etc. Mobile telecommunication is also consuming significant amount of power which also leads to CO₂ emissions. Next we are considering the portable devices like laptops and mobile phones. May be the popularity of Wi-Fi is one of the reasons for the usage of laptops become more frequent. Mobile phones and related telecommunication infrastructure are also contributing to the total energy consumption, so their role can't be ignored. The energy required to keep a network which consists of devices like routers, switches, firewall etc in running state is also considerable when we are thinking of total consumed energy.

6. TECHNIQUES FOR POWER MANAGEMENT

1. In Compilers

Run time analysis of programs using energy aware compilers is done. Then the code is again shaped by applying green aspects during transformation phase. The strategies can be applied at local global and inter procedural level.

(A) Instruction Grouping

By clustering and executing instructions in one cycle we can conserve energy effectively. Compilers with specific architecture can do this.

(B) Instruction Reordering

By changing the order of instructions also we can save energy. For Power safe mode to be established reordering plays a significant role.

(C) Construction of Energy cost tree

By creating an energy cost database for each instruction, the compilers can store energy cost. This database can be used in phases like code parsing and parse tree generation algorithms.

(D) Loop optimization and Memory partitioning

The loop optimization is an efficient technique to increase execution speed and reduce the overhead associated with loops. Also it plays a significant role in improving cache performance. Thus loop optimization is a very good strategy for power management.

(E) Dynamic Power management

Power consumption in CMOS is classified into static and dynamic. This scheme sets power of its hardware as per the demand, by adopting dynamic scheme we can assure that there will not be any power leakage.

(F) Resource Hibernation

Enabling low power mode is the process of hibernation. But the process of switching from and to this state consumes resources and time.

(G) Eliminate Recursion

Recursion procedure using stack is time consuming and it takes lot of space and is also consuming energy when executed by a compiler.

(H) Cache skipping

In this technique compiler needs to separate blocks that has less chance of execution. In some cases there is no need of cache and hence we can consume power.

By implementing these techniques we can reduce power consumption up to an extent. From compiler point of view, we tried to optimize energy resources by managing resources in an efficient way.

2. *At Software Level*

Energy conservation is implemented at various stages of software development life cycle (SDLC) phases such as analysis, design and implementation. By making an energy efficient software structure at the design phase we can save energy.

A. Using Green Compiler

Many energy aware compilers are available. These can be used effectively for energy conservation.

B. Ready to use computer resources

Making use of ready to use resources saves energy, cost and time.

C. Practise Iteration

Because of the more execution time needed for recursion, it consumes more energy. So it is better to go for iteration.

D. Usage of Algorithms and Data structures

By selecting Algorithms with less time complexity and also by taking efficient data structures we can save energy.

3. *At Hardware Level*

A. Dynamic Voltage and Frequency Scaling (DVFS)

This technique is used to reduce supply voltage of a processor when the work load is too less. Then the processor can reduce the speed but is still giving a performance that is enough to meet system requirements.

B. Implementation of Sleep mode

After finishing the execution the system can be turned into sleep mode for conservation of energy.

C. Energy Efficient Algorithms

By selecting appropriate algorithms we can save energy without any performance issues.

4. *Data Centre Design*

A. Efficient Servers

Servers are responsible for most of the energy wastage. When purchasing new servers, we have to select the one with variable speed fans for internal cooling which in-turn saves energy.

B. Power supplies

By using higher efficiency power supplies we can reduce a data centre's power bills and also it will reduce cooling system cost.

C. Virtualization

Virtualization level handles power management in a different way. It uses virtual machines for effectively manage power. By creating a number of virtual machines on the server, we can effectively reduce the number of hardware and also on the other hand we can efficiently improve the utilization of resources.

D. Network Equipment

By selecting energy management measures like gate count optimization, memory access algorithms, I/O buffer reduction we can reduce energy usage.

7. CONCLUSION

Green IT will be the driving force of future computing. This paper focuses on analyzing Green IT techniques for managing power and energy in computing system. The techniques we have discussed minimize energy consumption thereby minimizes power bill. By using non toxic materials for making equipments we can assure that the worker is safe from health problems. There is a need of appropriate regulations, user education and awareness about the need of

energy consumption and for minimizing environmental waste. By strictly following the techniques for energy conservation, computers can be made more energy efficient. This paper also briefly discusses the major energy consumers in computing. By following the Green IT techniques we can maintain the balance of nature.

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